

Thrombosis Rates and Complications Associated with the Denali Inferior Vena Cava Filter: A Review of Clinical Evidence in Peer Reviewed Literature

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Abstract

Inferior vena cava filters are utilized to prevent pulmonary embolism in patients with contraindications to anticoagulation. Despite advancements in filter design, complications such as deep vein thrombosis and IVC thrombosis remain areas of concern. This article reviews data from recent studies to evaluate the rates of thrombosis specifically associated with the BD/Bard Denali IVC filter. Findings indicate that the Denali filter is associated with a significantly elevated risk of caval thrombosis relative to other IVC filter models, warranting careful consideration in patient selection and monitoring protocols.

Keywords: Denali, Bard, BD, Thrombosis, IVC, DVT

1. Introduction

The use of IVC filters has expanded to include patients at high risk for thromboembolic events, particularly those unable to receive anticoagulation therapy. While the Denali filter, manufactured by Bard Peripheral Vascular, was designed to minimize complications such as filter migration, penetration, and fracture, emerging evidence has highlighted concerns related to increased thrombosis risk associated with the IVC filter. This review summarizes findings from multiple studies to provide a comprehensive analysis of thrombosis rates linked to the Denali filter.

2. Study Summaries and Thrombosis Findings

(Xiao et al.,2022)

In a comprehensive study by Xiao et al. (2022), thrombosis risks associated with various IVC filters were assessed across a cohort of 1,582 patients. The study reported thrombosis rates among several commonly used filters, providing insights into comparative risk levels. The Denali IVC filter was associated with a markedly higher rate of thrombosis compared to

other filter models, with a thrombosis incidence of 10.0% and an odds ratio of 8.9 (95% CI: 2.5, 31.8), which was statistically significant ($p = .001$). After multivariable adjustments, the Denali filter maintained an OR of 6.1 (95% CI: 1.6, 23.3; $p = .008$), suggesting a consistently elevated risk profile. In comparison to the Denali filter's 10% thrombosis rate observed among 50 filters, other IVC filters demonstrated significantly lower risks:

ALN Filter (445 filters): Exhibited the lowest rate at 1.1%, serving as the reference standard. Cook Medical Celect Filter (529 filters): Had a moderate thrombosis rate of 2.1%, indicating a controlled risk. Bard Medical G2 Filter (50 filters): Showed a similar rate to the Celect at 2.0%, reflecting minor variation within Bard's models. Argon Medical Option Filter (125 filters): Reported a low thrombosis rate of 1.6%, underscoring a favorable risk profile. Cook Medical Gunther Tulip Filter (218 filters): Presented a moderate risk at 3.7%, higher than other filters but still well below the Denali's rate in comparison.

(Jain et al., 2024)

Jain et al. provided comprehensive data on thrombus burden and retrieval outcomes for the Denali filter, with a sample of 508 filters placed between 2015 and 2022. Caval thrombosis was noted in 5.2% of patients, with 4.2% of thrombosis cases identified via retrieval venogram and an additional 8.9% detected through follow-up imaging in patients whose filters were not retrieved at the study site. Notably, 6.3% of cases had thrombus within the filter upon initial retrieval, with some cases showing a thrombus burden exceeding 30%, which necessitated additional retrieval attempts.

The study also highlights a strong correlation between longer dwell times and increased risk of thrombosis, emphasizing that early retrieval may mitigate some thrombotic risks.

These findings underscore both the importance of vigilant post-placement imaging and the feasibility of successful retrieval, particularly with structured follow-up. This data reinforces the need for careful patient selection and timely retrieval planning for the Denali filter to optimize safety and reduce thrombotic complications which were higher in this study than the associated thrombosis risks seen in similar studies for other brands of IVC filters.

(Stavropoulos et al., 2016)

Conducted as a prospective, multicenter trial, this study evaluated 200 patients with temporary indications for IVC filtration. Over a two-year follow-up, the incidence of new or worsening DVT was observed in 13% of patients. Although this data includes new DVT occurrences without distinguishing caval thrombosis specifically, the reported rates underscore the potential for thrombotic events following Denali filter placement. This finding may suggest a need for rigorous monitoring in patients receiving the Denali filter, especially those with a predisposition to thrombotic events.

3. Discussion

The cumulative data from these studies point to what is possibly an elevated thrombosis risk associated with the Denali IVC filter, particularly when compared to other filter models. The study by Xiao et al. underscore the statistical association between the Denali filter and higher incidences of ilio caval thrombosis, which may be attributed to design factors or specific patient demographics prone to thrombotic complications. The findings from Jain

et al. further illustrate that caval thrombosis associated with the Denali filter can often be identified at the time of retrieval, which emphasizes the importance of early follow-up imaging and retrieval when clinically appropriate.

The Stavropoulos et al. study while reporting a lower rate of specific caval thrombosis, recorded an elevated 13% rate of new or worsening DVT which stands higher than other retrievable filters in similar designed studies. These findings may represent thrombotic events distal to the filter or adjacent to the filter site, suggesting that the thrombotic potential of the Denali filter is not isolated to the IVC itself but may extend to peripheral venous sites.

4. Conclusion

In referenced peer reviewed studies, the Bard Denali IVC filter demonstrated a higher-than-average risk of thrombosis compared to other IVC filters in similar designed studies.

Given the increased rate of thrombosis and associated implications, patient selection criteria should prioritize short-term use, with close monitoring and early retrieval where possible. Further research is warranted to understand the mechanisms driving thrombosis in patients with the Denali IVC filter and whether the design of the filter may contribute to the elevated thrombosis rates seen in these studies, or if other factors not specifically related to the filter design contributed to the elevated rates of thrombosis demonstrated.

This literature review is subject to several limitations. First, heterogeneity among included studies may impact the generalizability of the findings, as individual studies varied in patient populations, IVC filter types, indications for placement, and follow-up durations. The lack of randomized controlled trials in some included data reduces the strength of causal inferences regarding filter placement and DVT incidence. Additionally, reporting bias may be present, as studies with significant findings on thrombosis rates are more likely to be published than those with non-significant results, potentially skewing pooled estimates.

5. References

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Figure 1: Bard Denali IVC Filter

Figure 2: Thrombosed IVC With Thrombus Above And Below Denali IVC Filter